

Navigating TechCentral's Film Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

Contents

Foreword	3
Methodology	3
Acknowledgements	3
1 Definition and Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem	5
2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map	6
3 Leverage Proposal	8
3.1 What and Why: Vision and Future State of the Ecosystem	8
3.1.1 Leverage Proposal 1	9
3.1.2 Leverage Proposal 2	10
References	11

1 Definition and Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Entrepreneurial ecosystem can be defined as multiple components of an entrepreneurial system, that is combined creating and forming an ecosystem. Entrepreneurial activity is present in every part of the world. It is crucial for every country that they have a stable entrepreneurial ecosystem (Mack & Mayer, 2015). Entrepreneurial ecosystem differs for every country. Entrepreneurial ecosystems have different aspects such as finance, human capital, development, culture, support, stability and more (Feld, 2012). Some examples of areas full of entrepreneurial activity across the world are Oxford England (Lawton-Smith, et al. 2013), Pharmaceuticals cluster (Mason & Brown, 2014), Silicon Valley (Saxenian, 1994). These places created a positive entrepreneurial ecosystem in their own unique way. Moreover, Australia is currently planning to create the next Silicon Valley. The plan already is a project now involving Australian government and successful entrepreneurs. However, before discussing the future, it is important to know the history of Australia's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

The idea of an entrepreneurial ecosystem as well as entrepreneurial hubs is relatively new to the world. Innovation itself has been implemented for hundreds of years. Australia is one of the most successful countries economically and in terms of innovation. There are historical innovations that came from Australia that are very useful for the world today. One of the earliest innovations in Australia is an Aboriginal technology called Didgeridoo. Didgeridoo is an instrument which usually is referred as drone pipe, musicologists usually describe it as an aerophone. This instrument was invented before the year 1788 and one of the most advanced instruments at the time (Cheal, 2007). In the year 1856, James Harrison produced one of the most innovative appliances that the world still uses until today which is the refrigerator. The refrigerator was the first ice making machine. At the time it was a breakthrough of technology not only for Australia but the world (Harrison, 1862).

These innovations were invented in the colonial era, in the 20th century post federation, there are some notable inventions Australia came up with such as surf ski, coupé utility car, feature film, dethridge wheel and electronic pacemaker. Until today, surf ski and coupé car is still being used across the globe making them one of the world's most successful inventions (White Hta, 2021). These inventions boost Australia's entrepreneurial ecosystem in the year 1901 until 1945.

In 20th century post-world war two, atomic absorption spectrophotometer, solar hot water, distance measuring equipment (DME) was developed by the CSIRO in Australia and became operational in Australia. Technology in Australia is also getting more advanced. Bionic ear was created, race cam was installed, medical ultrasound was invented, CPAP mask became a treatment and one of the most crucial inventions was wi-fi. CSIRO researchers patented a method to unsmear radio waves that echo off indoor surfaces (Australian Academy of Science, 2007). With this method, Wi-Fi was attributed as an Australian invention. Australia had a lot of inventions in the year 1946-2000 making Australia one of the strongest countries economically. Australia's entrepreneurial ecosystem is shaped by their inventions mostly in this timeline. Not only technological aspects but in film industry, medical, automotive, consumer products, finance, social, industrial, sport, entertainment, communication as well (Beveridge, 2016).

Film was first introduced to Australia in the mid-1800s when the first motion picture arrived using a kinoscope, which was soon followed by the construction of a kinoscope parlour in Pitt Street in 1884 and the first projected film for a paying audience two years later (Screen Australia 2020). By the early 1900s, the film industry was well established in Australia, particularly in Sydney and Melbourne. By 1920, the first colour films had been exhibited in Australia, and over 20 continuous cinemas were operating within Sydney (Glover, 2019). Hollywood had also emerged as a dominant film and video producer worldwide and had opened branches in Australia to distribute films, drastically expanding the film production ecosystem within Sydney (Cunningham, 1983). During this time, cinemas were wired for sound, and film quickly rose to prominence, becoming the most popular form of entertainment in Australia, ultimately prompting the formation and establishment of several film companies, including Longford-Lyell Productions, Fox Movietone newsreel and Cinesound Productions (National Film and Sound Archive 2020). Film and cinema continued to rise in popularity in WW2, with admissions and profits steadily increasing, as the public turned to entertainment as an escape and drive-in cinemas emerged nationwide. The first Sydney Film Festival took place in 1954, providing a significant opportunity for the development of the film community and showcasing of talent, and Charles Chavel's film *Jedda* became the first Australian feature to be shot and released in colour the following year, marking an all-time peak in Australian film (Screen Australia 2020).

The introduction of television occurred in Australia in the mid-1950s. By the end of the 1960s, cinema admissions had dropped drastically due to the growing preference for watching film from home

(Cunningham, 1983). This period also notably included the formation of Televisions Seven Network and Nine Network, The Australian Cinematographers Society and Australia's Film Institute, exponentially expanding the film production ecosystem technically, locally and globally. During this time, UNESCO also recommended film industry support.

Colour televisions were introduced to Australia in 1975, and by 1978 two thirds of households throughout Sydney and Melbourne had a coloured television (Screen Australia 2020).

Moreover, the increased interest in film and television across Australia encouraged the Launch of Film Australia and the establishment of the Australian Film Television and Radio School (AFTRS 2020). By the 1980s, SBS television had launched, TV services were slowly becoming subscriber based and the first official Australian-NZ co-production on a film occurred. With the film industry thriving globally and within Australia, Sydney began to establish itself as a leading and modern film production location within the wider ecosystem.

In the space of two decades, Australia's SPAA was formed, the largest cinema in the world was created in Darling Harbour, Fox Studios Sydney opened, ACMI opened, and the funding bodies merged to form Screen Australia (National Film and Sound Archive 2020). The 21st Century has since seen a continual development within Sydney's film industry ecosystem as world-class production centres are built, film production courses being offered are increasing, and local talent have more funding and opportunities.

2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

The entrepreneurial ecosystem in Sydney is rapidly growing, covering a wide range of industries. The purpose of our ecosystem map is to show our primary and secondary stakeholders for the creative and arts sector. We grouped our stakeholders into: startups, accelerators/incubators, government organisations, corporate companies, education, and the general public.

Although Tech Central does not exist yet, it is placed in the centre of our map to help us identify where the current links are and how the ecosystem could provide more connections. David Thodey, the chair for Jobs for NSW, is a primary stakeholder for developing the space around Central Station to be the innovation precinct, with startups, venture capitalists, creative companies and universities circling the cluster (Australian Government, 2019). Atlassian's new headquarters will also be at Tech Central, being at the heart of the precinct. This will open many opportunities for stakeholders to network and collaborate from all industries.

Surrounding the immediate area of Tech Central are: Sydney Startup Hub and government bodies in the North; UNSW, Fox Studios and many startups in the east; the former Australian Technology Park in the south; and UTS, USYD and the ABC in the west.

Our map uses an image from Google Maps of Sydney because we wanted to show the viewer that these stakeholders are relatively close together. This can be achieved when it be viewed on a single page. Our EE map is of the current and the future of the ecosystem. Removing Tech Central and Atlassian from the map will remain our stakeholders in their current locations and the network. The future of the ecosystem with Tech Central will ultimately lead to stronger links between stakeholders from one side of the city to the other because our stakeholders direct to the innovation precinct.

The map also identifies where the stakeholder groups are typically occupying. For example, education has a significant cluster around Ultimo and Camperdown, government bodies located in the CBD, and startups and production companies in Surry Hills and Moore Park.

However, Google Maps allows us to identify the gaps where there are minimal stakeholders for the industry. Southern Sydney suburbs and Darlinghurst surround the CBD and Tech Central, yet very few stakeholders that we have identified occupy these regions. Thus, this presents an opportunity for future stakeholders to use the space to spark innovation for these suburbs. South Eveleigh is one of these suburbs that has plans to be part of innovation. The Mirvac organisation is using the land, history, and culture to re-imagine the space (South Eveleigh, n.d.). Formerly known as the Australian Technology Park, Eveleigh and Redfern will be the closest suburbs of the Cleveland Street sub-precinct for Tech Central, presenting the opportunity for community growth and innovation (The Urban Developer, 2020).

A legend has been created for the viewer to identify stakeholder groups quickly. The legend also shows the strength between stakeholders as some have stronger links than others. All the stakeholders we have identified have a solid connection to the Tech Central precinct, with dotted lines to show the relationships around the map to other stakeholders.

The NSW and local government are significant stakeholders for the creative industry. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, they have become crucial in supporting these businesses and keeping jobs to improve our economy. In 2013, Australia's creative and cultural sector produced \$90 Billion to the economy (SGS, 2020). The industry was one of the most affected by the coronavirus because of a sharp decrease in demand, requiring assistance from the government to keep Sydney's and Australia's culture alive. Create NSW is a government organisation assisting these businesses and independent artists (Create NSW, n.d.).

The general public is listed on our map because the business model of many art and production companies is to provide engaging content and entertainment for people. Without support from the general public, artists and businesses will financially struggle to reach their budget. The pandemic has emphasised this problem with government restrictions for venue capacity and lockdowns. This is why on our map, the general public connects with every stakeholder we have identified because the innovation precinct is one big community. Likewise, with universities, there are fewer local and international students enrolling in courses such as UTS Animal Logic or UNSW Art & Design because of the pandemic. Evidently, this leads to a sharp decrease in revenue, forcing jobs to be lost and pay cuts.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 What and Why: Vision and Future State of the Ecosystem

As seen in the 'Evolution of our Ecosystem', the Internet video industry, specifically the entire European and American entertainment markets have undergone an entire reinvention in the past decade. Hence, facing constant changes to the overall economic environment and the internal industry ecosystem, we are interested and looking forward to the future of this ever-changing industry.

Despite reaching out to numerous stakeholders in the ecosystem, we unfortunately only received one interview response from Duco Van Breemen, CEO of Haymarket HQ (see appendix 1). While Duco's response focused primarily on the startup ecosystem as he is an indirect stakeholder of the creative and film industries, we were hoping we would receive a response in time from a stakeholder within the creative industries too. Hence our vision and future state of the film industry was primarily based on in-depth research and reports. In saying that, Duco's response was still very appreciated. It allowed us to further our knowledge of the Sydney startup ecosystem and understand the changes an industry expert hopes to see in the near future such as "Australia to build a global reputation that extends beyond that of an exporter of primary produce".

Despite further technological advancements, and evolving user needs, business models, and content, video platforms will continue to dominate over the next decade. Interestingly, a study by Forbes predicted by 2030 traditional TV subscriptions will decrease by 27% as streaming through smartphones, laptops, and other devices on video online platforms continue to significantly increase (Forbes, 2020). Hence, our first leverage involves a cooperative online community.

The video production industry can also be understood as a content creation industry such as digital marketing. Video advertising is now the most profitable and versatile digital marketing tool. Over 4 billion videos are watched every day on YouTube, and by 2022 video traffic will account for 83% of all traffic online (Cisco, 2020). Hence, our second leverage proposes strengthening the relationship between startups and video marketing in our EE to take advantage of the significant response and future growth of this digital marketing tool.

Although in the free market, the amount of supply does not exactly equal the amount of demand. We hope that through our work, we can help companies in the ecosystem to embark on a path to scale. Through the establishment of community or development cooperation, each company in the industry can have its own unique direction and future.

3.1.1 Leverage Proposal 1

Question

Based on a study of the video industry startup ecosystem in the Sydney area, our group found that while there are many startup organizations and incubators. But the industry's content start-ups still have not been able to scale up and grow into full-fledged video studios. At the same time, some of the larger streaming platforms continue to emphasize their investment in original content. Stakeholders in the region do not have a platform to find the right partners.

Opportunity Areas

Enriching cooperation communities to create high-quality original content and create a win-win ecosystem.

The importance of content for a video is undeniable. Startups or established video companies already understand the importance of consistently delivering quality content and the ultimate service, and they use content to increase user loyalty and satisfaction with video platforms (Martins & Riyanto, 2020). In the future, the video industry will invest more in self-produced content and original scripts. Users will be the main decision-makers in choosing which story topics to focus on. New content trends are slowly taking shape at scale as a result of this push.

The definition of "quality" will be more subjective. The users will not only want to see good content, but also content that meets their preferences. To better meet the needs of our customers, they will be increasingly segmented. Creative studios are emerging.

Streaming platforms are not only developing content by themselves (Trainer, 2019), but also outsourcing. Compared to the past, the number of start-up content studios in the video industry has increased significantly, and they are covering more topics and forms of presentation. In addition to big investment films dominating the box office, smaller studios will be able to attract audiences in niche areas with avant-garde offerings (Yao, 2019), and quality content will emerge in different niche categories.

Video/streaming platforms and content companies should choose to collaborate and attempt to develop joint projects by combining the strengths of both parties (Wenlock, 2019). If the video production company agrees to work with the content producer, then there are many benefits for both parties. On one hand, a household name streaming site has lots of users, and the business product created in combination with such a company undoubtedly has a non-negligible advantage in the competitive market. Secondly, online streaming has a wide audience and a long viewing time per capita, which undoubtedly increases traffic and exposure for content companies. And for streaming platforms, choosing the right content company means bringing more high quality original content and original creators. Streaming platforms no longer need to invest too much money in creating video content. This cooperation is undoubtedly a contribution to the sustainable development of the video industry startup ecosystem in the Sydney region.

Leverage and Accelerator

We found that building an online community can help facilitate collaboration among industry stakeholders. Each participating organization/startup/stakeholder in the industry can sign up for an official account. They can show their company history, projects they are building, their geographic location, and future vision through posts. In such an online community, every company will be able to find partners that interest them.

Posts in the community can lead to collaboration between entrepreneurs. Browse through the content created by stakeholders in the community for the opportunity to find ideas that are similar or complementary to your business plan. Contact a startup that is geographically close to you for collaboration opportunities through real-time targeting. Perhaps the startup lacks startup capital and some large capital agency is looking for a good idea worth investing in. When collaboration is confirmed between businesses or individuals, experience and resources can be shared. The community also invites government departments that act as policymakers and Tech central acts as accelerators to stay in the community, increasing the opportunity to interact with players in the industry. Entrepreneurs and stakeholder organizations can connect directly within the community to exchange ideas.

3.1.2 Leverage Proposal 2

Opportunity

The second lever we are proposing includes strengthening the relationship between start-ups and video marketing in Sydney. While the first leverage focused on streaming platforms and creating an online community, this leverage centres around establishing a collaboration between start-ups and video production companies in order to build brand awareness, trust and sales through video marketing.

In this ever changing world, people want their information effortlessly and fast. It is critical for start-ups to produce effective and unique content that makes their product or service stand out, and while many companies look towards print, still ads on social media, telemarketing and email marketing, the single most critical marketing strategy today is video. Video is now the most profitable and versatile digital marketing tool.

Over 4 billion videos are watched every day on YouTube, and by 2022 video traffic will account for 83% of all traffic online (Cisco, 2020). Whether a company is using Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, or Snapchat, video is revolutionising marketing. Although an expensive marketing tool, an astonishing 47% of social media users who encounter a video advertisement online will engage with the brand, and around 73% of companies say video advertisement has increased their ROI (Statista, 2021).

Lever

Due to the significant growth and response of video advertising, we are proposing a collaboration between start-ups and video production in order to improve our entrepreneurial ecosystem. The integration of this form of digital marketing is critical for these start-ups and their marketing strategy in order to remain relevant and boost conversion rates at this crucial time in their business journey.

Accelerator

This could include a partnership between TechCentral and video marketing, a space within TechCentral for a video production company. The funding and current developing stage makes TechCentral an appropriate accelerator and choice to initiate this future change within the ecosystem. The relocation of a company would connect start-ups and scaleups, creating a collaborative and easily accessible space for entrepreneurial like-minded individuals and experienced marketers.

This would include pitching to TechCentral Industry Advisory Board to gain approval of the initiative, determining a new office layout and space within TechCentral, finding a video production company willing to relocate, and relocating resources, technology and equipment. As construction has not yet commenced, TechCentral and our leverage is estimated to be completed by 2025.

Value to Stakeholders

Through our first lever on a co-creation community, industry stakeholders can gain experience and find capital investment. Bringing benefits to the local area in many ways, such as successful cultural outreach and increased job opportunities, and economic gains:

- Macro-level: Meet the collaboration needs of stakeholders through a dynamic partnership structure that promotes sustainable industry growth.
- Micro-level: Bringing collaborative opportunities to each company to help them grow better in the industry.

Collaborative communities do not just provide opportunities for collaboration and bring financial benefits. More than that, it brings a place for the industry to exchange information and mutual resources. Even for start-ups, they can browse the latest industry news, watch those industry leaders interpret and understand the latest policies, and clarify their direction, which helps create an industry environment where information is actively exchanged.

Our second lever will strengthen the relationship between start-ups and video production within our entrepreneurial ecosystem. If TechCentral decides to adopt this lever, an increase in interactions, opportunities and a collaboration between differing industries and companies will prevail. The lever aligns with their aim of creating a collaborative space for thousands of workers and the best new ideas and innovations, a home for 'tech giants, innovative start-ups and leading talent to be all in one space' (NSW Gov 2020). However there is always a risk and cost of relocating a company into the space. Success is unknown and there are usually time contracts and commitments.

For start-ups within TechCentral, this leverage would provide a collaborative space for entrepreneurs, having access to experienced marketers within their own workspace. Although video advertising is an expensive marketing strategy, the pros heavily outweigh the cons. Video marketing helps communicate a brand's story and values through compelling visuals, boost conversion rates, increase brand awareness and earn customer trust. A great story can communicate a brand's entire character in less than three minutes (Walters, 2019).

For the video production company that would relocate to TechCentral, there would be an undoubtedly increase of traffic and exposure for the company with access to countless start-ups requiring video advertisements and campaigns. The relocation of headquarters comes with moving costs and risks of losing labour and clients.

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